

Landing over their head

Supplemental Materials

Instruction Manuals

Royal Naval Air Service. Kite balloon training manual, Air Department, Admiralty January 1917

Landing. On impact with the ground the knees should be bent as much as possible. If the observer has not previously released himself from the sling, but lands with it between his legs, he should throw himself on his back, with his legs in the air, so that the parachute can pull clear.

Precautions on Jumping. - Before jumping, it is advisable to fill the lungs by taking a deep breath, as after jumping no, which will breath can be taken until the parachute has opened not be for three or four seconds.

On approaching within a thousand feet of the ground the land should be studied in order to ascertain as far as possible on what the landing is likely to be made. If there is much wind blowing the observer may be dragged unless he is free from the parachute immediately on landing, and it is therefore advisable, before reaching the ground, to pull the body up by the arms and kick away the supporting sling, letting the full weight of the body come on to the arms. There is no danger in this, provided that it is not done too soon, the usual height being 500 feet or less. There is no advantage to be gained from doing it sooner.

Parachute manual for balloons 1919

The shock of landing should be absorbed as much as possible by bending the knees as one does when jumping from a wall. This applies to descents in basket parachutes as well to the individual parachute types.

Parachute Manual (1920) W 87.5:P 21/2 United States Army Air Service Engineering Division, United States Army Air Service Parachute Branch Equipment Section Engineering Division, Air Service, McCook Field, Dayton, Ohio, 1920

In landing, face the direction of the drift, if possible, but do not try to twist around just as the landing is to be made. If the legs are slightly bent, the shock will be better absorbed. No attempt should be made to stand up. Fig. 58 shows the proper attitude of the body just before landing. Sink in a loose position and roll if necessary. When landing in a high wind, unstrap the breast strap, take arms out of the shoulder strap, and unfasten the leg straps while descending, in order to be free from the harness when landing.

GYMNICH Flugpraxis C12 1927

By bending your knees slightly and tensing your muscles, you absorb the impact of the landing. (Durch eine leichte Kniebeuge und Anspannen der Muskeln fängt man den Landungsstoß ab.)

Russel Lobe Parachute 1928

Upon landing, let your knees bend under you as you would if jumping from a six-foot elevation.

WD AC TM2170-72 Parachute Rigger 1929

39. Making a parachute landing.-A parachute landing should always be made with the wind (back toward the wind). The most important thing to remember when making a landing is not to stiffen the legs but to maintain an attitude as though preparing to make a jump. When nearing the ground during descent, grasp the main risers of the right main group of shroud lines in one hand and the risers of the left main group of shroud lines in the other so as to be erect at the time of landing. Hang- ing on to the risers in this manner also helps to break the fall when coming in contact with the ground. The distance from the ground is sometimes hard to determine ; therefore it is considered good practice to watch the horizon as well as the ground during descent and not stare directly at the ground. The distance to the ground can generally be judged more accurately in this man- ner than by staring directly at the ground. Keep the knees slightly bent, with the feet not over

12 inches apart, pulling down on the risers when striking the ground. Do not try to stand erect. Break the force of the fall by falling over.

Parachutes Mumma, J. V.

1930

Since a parachute landing should always be made with the back towards the wind, it may be necessary to change position with reference to the wind direction preparatory to landing. This may be done by grasping a main lift web in each hand and whipping the a manner so as to turn the parachute and the user facing in the correct position. Preparatory to landing grasp one of the rear lift webs in each hand. If the legs are slightly stiffened, the knees bent and the heels together, the impact upon reaching the ground will be lessened. THE impact of landing will also be reduced if the jumper does not try to remain erect after landing.

Distance from the ground may be better: determined by watching the horizon rather than looking straight down.

Parachutes for airmen, Dixon

1930

To minimize the shock of landing, the legs must not be held stiffly but drawn up in a sitting position, whilst it is best to fall over naturally than attempt a standing landing. A foot or so above ground is the position to grasp the shroud lines (those descending from the centre of the canopy apex) and pull down hard therefore collapsing the canopy and preventing drag along the ground.

Irvin Air Chutes

1937

Landing

Flex the knees slightly but not too much, relax, land limber and loose—and don't try to stand erect but let the body follow its natural tendency of direction and motion as you contact the earth. In picture at left, note how gently the aviator's feet touch the ground. The patented IRVIN Harness permits him to further ease his landing by grasping the harness webs over his head and pulling against the canopy as his feet touch ground. Thus, the IRVIN Air Chute provides an easier landing than other parachutes with a canopy of the same diameter and rate of descent.

Jordanoff Your Wings

1938

It is a good practise, just prior to the instant of your making contact with the ground, to have your body and legs completely relaxed, thus lessening the shock considerably. 38 In addition try your best contact the ground with your back toward the wind

Civil Aeronautics Bulletin 20

1939

LANDING

A parachute landing should be made with the back toward the wind. It is important to remember not to stiffen the legs but to maintain an attitude as though preparing to make a jump. When near the ground during descent, the main risers of the right main group of shroud lines should be grasped in one hand and the risers of the left main group of shroud lines in the other so as to be erect at the time of landing. Hanging onto the risers in this manner also helps to break the fall when coming in contact with the ground. The distance from the ground may be ascertained more accurately by watching the horizon as well as the ground during descent. The knees should be kept slightly bent, with the feet not over 12 inches apart. Pull down on the risers when striking the ground, and do not try to stand erect. The force of the fall may be broken by falling over.

Lusk General Aeronautics

1940

Parachute Landing. A parachute landing should be made with the back toward the wind and facing in the direction of travel. It is important to remember not to stiffen the legs but to maintain a flexed position as though preparing to make a jump. When near the ground, the right hand should grasp the risers on that side and the left hand the risers on the left side. Supporting the body in this manner assures an erect position when landing and also lessens the shock when contacting the ground. Altitude may best be judged by watching the horizon as well as the ground during descent. The knees should be kept slightly bent but tensed, so the knees will not collapse and strike the jumper's face. The feet should be spaced about

12 in. apart. A violent pull on the risers at the time of contact will decrease the landing shock. A jumper is advised not to try to stand erect ; the fall may be broken by falling over.

Civil Aeronautics Bulletin 23

1941

A parachute landing should be made with the back toward the wind. It is important to remember not to stiffen the legs but to maintain an attitude as though preparing to make a jump. When near the ground during descent, the main risers of the right main group of shroud lines should be grasped in one hand and the risers of the left main group of shroud lines in the other so as to be erect at the time of landing. Hanging onto the risers in this manner also helps to break the fall when coming in contact with the ground. The distance from the ground may be ascertained more accurately by watching the horizon as well as the ground during descent. The knees should be kept slightly bent, with the feet not over 12 inches apart. Pull down on the risers when striking the ground, and do not try to stand erect. The force of the fall may be broken by falling over.

Parachutes, Aircraft fabric and clothing TM 1-440

1941

d. As soon as the parachute has opened following a jump, the suspension lines should be observed for any twists. If twisted, they should be immediately pulled into their proper positions. During the descent the jumper should attempt to face the direction of the drift. He should also observe closely his distance from the ground, so as to be prepared to absorb the landing shock with his legs partly flexed. Landing in a rigid standing posture, or with the back toward the direction of drift, should never be attempted. Practice or training jumps are made only with the type T training parachutes, and under the condition outlined in AR 95-15. Such jumps are made in not more than a 10-mile wind and at not less than an altitude of 1,500 feet. The standard circular parachute is not maneuverable and little is accomplished by trying to guide it in any direction.

Parachutes, Fechet

1942

The landing should, if possible, be made facing down wind. On approaching the ground the sitting position should be retained and the muscle relaxed. No attempt should be made to take the shock of landing by stiffening the muscles. The lift webs should be grasped as far as possible above the head; and at the moment of impact the body should be given a hard pull upwards to assist in absorbing the landing shock. The body should be allowed to sink and if necessary roll over. Difficulty is sometimes found in judging the height from the ground; the best method is to glance alternatively at the ground vertically below and the horizon. Large errors are possible if the eyes are focused continuously on the ground.

Floyd Smith Parachutes

1942

A lightly loaded parachute is affected by air currents to a greater extent than is a heavily loaded chute and more and larger swings result. Landings are variously described as equal to a fall of 6 ft., 8 ft., 10 ft. or 12 ft., which is false. A fall of 5 ft., is equivalent to a rate of descent of 18 ft. per second, which is about the average for the 24 ft. chute under good conditions. A fall of 8 ft. is equivalent to a rate of descent of 22.5 ft. per second which is about average for bad conditions. When about to land, lean forward and bend the legs slightly, and fall forward after striking the ground. If a landing should be made backward, relax and roll. Never put your arms back of you or out to break a fall. A much easier landing can be made by reaching high above the head and grasping two opposite risers and pulling sharply just as you strike the ground. It is necessary that this maneuver be timed correctly. Do not pull until you know you are going to touch the ground

Bureau of Aeronautics Parachute Sense

1943

Stay in your sitting position with your knees normally bent as you touch the ground.

And pull the lift webs down sharply as you touch. This will prevent going over on your head at the impact, and will also slow your last seconds of descent.

Make no other effort to maintain an upright position. If you now find you have a tendency to fall or roll, relax and GIVE.

You know enough by now to know why you should follow that advice, and not stiffen to fight the impact.

A relaxed, rolling fall can't hurt you.

Zweng Parachute Technician

1944

Landing: It is good practice when preparing to land to retain a sitting position in the harness, but with the knees lower than the hips, and body relaxed. Grasp the lift webs over the head and at the moment the feet touch the ground, before the parachute can collapse, lift the body up by pulling down on the lift webs, sink in a relaxed position and roll if necessary. Do not attempt to stand up. This is considered the easiest method but must be timed accurately. A common method when

17 Watch your drift and try to land facing the drift. Landing in a rigid standing position, or with the back toward the direction of drift, should never be attempted

19 When about to land, lean forward and bend the legs slightly, and fall forward after striking the ground

Landing instruction found in popular accounts

Year	Author	Landing instruction
1839	Hampton	Reach... the ground under the most perfect quiet and pleasing gravity
1887	T. S. Baldwin	Generally, I have landed without doing myself any harm. When I see I am within six or seven feet of the ground I drop. Then land pretty well on my toes, and if I feel momentum which would be likely to throw me violently down, I try to fall on my right side, and sometimes I turn three or four somersaults, this breaks the force, of course
1909	Penfold	You reach the ground as if in a free drop from a height of about 4 ft.
1917	Antarcticus	Third and fourth day.—Instruction in correct method of alighting (teeth closed, toes pointed down, knees turned out), practice in jumping down from various heights on to various surfaces.
1917	Antichute	It is all very well talking about parachutes, but how on earth, or rather in the air, are we to be instructed in the use of them? No doubt most of us could, in an emergency, do what we wouldn't care to do in cold blood, but if I were suddenly detailed to go through a course of parachuting my comment would be "Not in these trousers"
1920	Neumann	(1918) During landing, the legs are slightly bent to absorb the impact, having first aligned oneself with the wind direction to land facing forward.
1920	Neumann	(Steinbrecher, 1918) As I approached the ground, I bent my legs slightly to absorb the landing. Despite this, the impact was quite hard, and I tumbled backward into a shell crater.
1920	Neumann	(Kromer, 1918) At around 500 meters, I removed my goggles to avoid interference during landing. I prepared for the impact with a slight bend in my knees and quickly assessed where I would touch down. Everything worked perfectly.
1920	Anon.	The jumper should also be instructed to release his reserve chute when about 100 to 150 feet from the ground, to lessen his weight when striking the ground. He should be instructed to turn his body so that he faces with the wind when descending, as he has a better chance of keeping his feet when landing.
1920	Gas Bag	Even a bad landing will result usually in not more than a hearty shaking-up
1921	M. Blanquier	C'est ainsi que l'atterrissage peut être dangereux avec un parachute trop petit. Celui qui me sert à 9 m. 50 de diamètre, mais je puis en utiliser un de 8 m. 50, car je suis léger et vous savez que la surface sustentatrice doit être en fonction du poids de l'expérimentateur. Landing with an undersized parachute is dangerous. I am jumping with a 31.2 feet canopy, but I can jump as well with a smaller 27.9 feet canopy because I am lightweight.
1921	M. Blanquier	Il ne faut jamais essayer de toucher le sol avec les pieds ; on est généralement surpris par celui -ci avant d'avoir fait toute réaction. Une fois sur cent, on atterrira sur les pieds, ..., selon que l'air sera plus ou moins porteur près de terre. D'une façon générale, une descente devient plus rapide à l'approche du sol: le mieux est de se mettre un peu en « boule ». Vouloir atterrir droit, c'est courir le risque de se casser une jambe. Never reach for the ground with your feet; one is generally caught off guard by the landing. On rare occasions, a standing landing happens, ..., depending on how much lift the air provides near the ground. Typically, a descent becomes faster when nearing the ground: the best approach is to tuck oneself into a rounded posture. An upright landing carries the risk of breaking a leg.
1921	T. Orde-Lees	(after facing downwind) He (Taylor) then brought his legs straight back under his body and found himself in the correct. position for landing. The landing itself was carried out with about the same impact as that one gets when jumping off a motor bus going at a moderate

Year	Author	Landing instruction
		speed. After touching the ground, he immediately ran forward so as to release the pressure of the wind in the parachute as it blew forward into a horizontal position.
1924	H. R. Harris	I remembered that the proper thing to do in landing was to pull one's legs up as if about to land on the ground after jumping off a high board fence. I also remembered that by grasping the parachute webbing with the arms, additional assistance could be got in retarding the shock of landing.
1926	M. Wright	When the feet appear to be three or four feet above the ground the jumper pulls himself up as if he were on a horizontal bar. This greatly reduces the shock. Otherwise, the impact for a 154-pound man would be equivalent to a jump off a ten-foot wall.
1926	J. Pearson	In landing, the feet should be close together and the knees somewhat bent. No effort should be made to stand up and the body should be relaxed. Rolling over absorbs the shock of the fall to some extent, and one is less apt to be hurt in taking the tumble than in trying too hard to resist one. Some try to roll over backward while others prefer to fall forward in the direction in which they are drifting, but as in most cases the inexperienced jumper has no choice in the matter. Either position, facing or back to the direction of drift will do sufficiently well.
1926	Crump	I realized that I was within fifty feet of the ground and it was time I prepared to make a landing. It is not the easiest thing in the world to land with a parachute and a great many serious injuries have been sustained because the jumper has become very careless on approaching the ground. No matter how slowly the 'chute falls, still the jumper's body comes in contact with the earth with jolting force. To counteract this it is customary to reach upward and hook one's hands into the D rings that hold the shrouds on either side of the meshed sling in which one sits. By lifting upward the parachute man can relax his body and at the moment of coming in contact with the earth take up the force of the impact so that he is not injured. I followed the prescribed method and when my feet came in contact with the earth I took up the strain of the fall and skidded along in the dust for probably a dozen feet until the weight of the parachute pulling out ahead of me yanked me over onto my back. It dragged me perhaps ten feet further before the 'chute men led out of the ambulance that had rumbling up, and pouncing upon the silken envelope, crushed the air out of its folds.
1927	G. H. Tavis (illustrator)	Easing the "bump" on landing (sketch w/ knee bent). Making a "pull up" of the body just as the feet are about to touch the ground.
1927	F. O. Soden	As the earth approaches, the speed of descent appears to increase, and some people are apt to lose their heads and stiffen up. The pupil is instructed to relax his muscles slightly, and land in much the same way as after jumping off a wall. He should not try and remain standing, as this is impossible; the best thing is to roll over. One does not float gently on to the ground as some people imagine, but at a rate of approximately 17ft. per second. If one jumps in earnest and only break s a couple of legs or arms, one has no right to grumble.
1928	N. M. Clark	So I opened the second 'chute, and, fortunately, it did what I wanted it to. But, better still, another change of air currents took me in a new direction, carrying me over the river. "I finally landed in ice-cold mountain water, but in a nice shallow place maybe ten feet from shore ; my 'chutes, of course, had to fall the wrong way, into the water!"
1928	Anon.	Hitting the ground with the parachute is like being in a fast elevator that strikes the bottom without slackening speed. The landing parachutist makes no attempt to stand up, but lets his legs buckle under him as if he had just made a ten-foot jump
1928	Whitby (Murphy)	...I had learned in previous jumps that by keeping my feet together and pointed out, in the manner of a runner sliding to base, I could materially lessen the landing shock.
1930	C. W. Purcell	As you come closer to the ground you remember your instructions about landing. You look around to find your wind direction—smoke from a factory chimney or the wind sock on the field will tell you this. Your bag will float the way the wind is blowing, and in this direction you will roll if you have to roll at all. Bringing up your knees as high as you can by holding them with your hands, you are ready to land. Don't forget to duck your head just as you hit, and roll over on your shoulder—in this way you kill some of the shock of You hit with a bump—you roll as directed someone jumps on your 'chute to flatten it.
1930	Murphy	Probably the most important need in approaching the ground is to hold the feet together, with the knee slightly bent. Under no conditions should a landing be made with the feet

Year	Author	Landing instruction
		spread apart or the knees stiff. When the jumper touches ground, he should not attempt to fight back the toppling pull of the parachute, or to attempt to remain erect... The wiser course is to allow the body to swing sideways, and, if possible, roll until the parachute has spilled out its air. This is done a second or two after it touches ground.... The legs should be slightly bent, as in a routine landing.
1937	Anon.	<p>The most dangerous part of jumping is the landing. The experienced jumper always tries to land on his toes with his knees slightly bent. Should keep his legs stiff or straight, they are liable to be broken by the force of the fall. Once on the ground, his job is to deflate the chute canopy lest it drag him along. To accomplish he either falls to the ground and worms himself up to the chute or else runs around to get the chute between himself and the wind.</p> <p>This young French parachutist is showing the correct way to land. Unlike Miss Rauner (above), he did not get his feet tangled in the shroud lines. He landed feet first, his knees slightly bent to absorb the shock. Immediately upon touching the ground he allowed himself to fall, thus preventing the parachute from dragging him across the field. Facing the open chute he is now crawling towards the canopy which he must deflate before to unfasten his parachute harness.</p>
1941	Finney	<p>A parachute landing should always be made with your back to the wind. You may thus find it necessary to change position with reference to the wind just before landing. To do this, grasp a main lift web in each hand and cross them above your head in the same manner that a child on a swing turns himself. Thus you can turn to face in any desired direction.</p> <p>Preparatory to landing, distance from the ground can always be judged better by reference to the horizon than by looking down at the ground. Just before the impact, grasp one of the rear lift webs in each hand, place the heels together and bend the knees slightly. The shock will be lighter if you do not try to remain erect after landing. Collapse the 'chute immediately upon landing. Easiest way to do this is to grasp the group of shroud lines nearest the bottom and run toward the 'chute. The canopy will flatten at once. It is not essential to make practice jumps in order to use a 'chute efficiently</p>
1944	Tobin	<p>Previously the jumpers were instructed to contact the ground with their feet shoulder width apart. Since June 12, 1943, a new landing technique has been taught. The feet are now held together with the ankles touching. This enables the jumper to more evenly distribute the landing impact to the metatarsal regions of both feet.</p>